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Language/LID: Lahu / 225

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Sources:

-Matisoff, James. *The Grammar of Lahu*. University of California Press: Berkeley, 1973
[gram = grammar]

-Matisoff, James. "Lahu" in *The Sino-Tibetan Languages*, G. Thurgood, R. La Polla, eds.,
Routledge: London, New York, 2003 [art. = article]

-Matisoff, James. *The Dictionary of Lahu*. University of California Press: Berkeley, 1988
[dic = dictionary]

-Lahu is an isolating tonal language.

-Morphemes consist almost exclusively of one tone-bearing syllable in the following form:
(C)V

-9 vowels

-7 tones

-“all 49 mathematically possible two-syllable tonal sequences freely occur in close
juncture” (gram, p. 27-28; see for examples of each combination)

-There are 24 consonants, but no consonant clusters and no syllable-final consonants

-/?/ is thus considered by Matisoff a tonal feature, as well as due to the fact that /?/ rarely
occurs syllable-initially, and then only optionally and for emphasis in imperatives (gram. p.
9).

Overall, each tone is stressed equally and every syllable has a tone. Completely
stressless (and therefore toneless) syllables are “excessively rare.” As a result, stress
doesn’t serve any morph-syntactic function. However, there are a few native functor-
morphemes which have reduced stress (gram p. 34):

1. *mâ* ‘not’, *tâ* ‘do not’ often reduced stress is rapid speech
2. noun prefix ǝ- frequently reduced stress

-The tone system has seven tones:

mid (unmarked in transcription)

high-rising (marked with /)

high-falling (^)

low-falling (\)

very low ()

high-checked (^?)

low-checked (\ ?) (the last two are checked by a glottal stop, which again Matisoff
analyses as a tonal feature - see above).

-“The Lahu tones do not exhibit any strictly automatic, phonologically conditioned sandhi-
behavior.” (gram. p. 27) and “Rather than automatic, phonologically conditioned interplay
with each other, the Lahu tones show a variety of grammatically conditioned
interrelationships.” (gram, p. 28)., **BUT**:

-phonological rule (gram. p. 10):

unchecked V' + V' --> V': (resulting surface vowel is under a long composite tone)

ex: /ŋà + à? + pè? + lâ + a/ --> [ŋàà? + pè? + lâa] *

I it.ACC give Pv Puf

‘please give it to me’

*see grammar page 10 or ask Josh for better description of the surface tonal structure (.rtf
can’t show this)

‘grammatically conditioned interrelationships’ with phonological consequences:

Basically, there seem to be two particles which can have a phonological effect on the
previous segment (but don’t always and thus aren’t really productive). These are the verb

particle /ò/ and the particle /è/; see below for the specifics.

-fusional non-rising diphthongs:

1) verb particle /ò/ 'change of state', 'completed action' (gramm, p. 16):

after a verb with the same tone (\), the final V of the verb and this particle are fused into a diphthong consisting of a single mora without affecting the quality of either V (fusional non-rising diphthongs):

/pè/ + /ò/ --> [pèò] (= one mora!) 'it's finished now'

/gà/ + /ò/ --> [gâò] (= one mora!) 'we have arrived already'

2) three homophonous particles /ɛ/ (gramm. p. 16-19) (I couldn't find any examples where /ɛ/ isn't in fact /è/):

a) unrestricted particle /è/ 'only':

-after central vowels (fusional non-rising diphthongs):

tê pè + ɛ/ --> [tê pèɛ̃]

one mouthful only 'only one mouthful'

-after back vowels (fusional rising diphthongs):

fusion with è deprives the back vowel of syllabicity; the peak of sonority is

displaced on the following vowel (gram. p. 19-20)

tê khô + è --> [tê khòè]

one word only 'only one word'

b) adverbial expressions of the form *qha* 'all' + verb + è 'adverbializing particle':

-after central vowels (fusional non-rising diphthongs):

qha + pè + è --> [qha pèè̃]

all finish P_{adv} 'completely'

-after back vowels (fusional rising diphthongs):

here, if the V of the verb is back, it is "likely" to be fused with è:

qha + cô + è --> [qha còè]

all be.correct P_{adv} 'correctly'

c) diminutive extentives of the form *chi* 'this' + adj (referring to measurable quantities) + è (diminutive for degree of adj):

-after central vowels (fusional non-rising diphthongs) (sometimes optional!):

chi + hí + è --> [hí] [hí è]

this size P_{dim} 'such a small one'

-after back vowels (fusional rising diphthongs):

chi + mu + è --> [chi m uè̃]

this high P_{dim} 'only this high'

Matisoff actually posits the following phonetic rule "of some generality concerning the phonetic realization of fusions between the central vowels /a ə i/ and a following /ɛ/. The underlying sequences /a-ɛ/ and /ə-ɛ/ are realized as [aɛ̃], while /i-ɛ/ is realized as [ĩ]"

(gram. p. 17); in other words:

/ɛ/ --> [ɛ̃] / a-__, e-__

/ɛ/ --> [ĩ] / i-__

In addition, there is a small group of "morphemes (notably five with meanings relating to color) which are under the mid-tone when functioning as nouns, but which acquire / / when followed by the adverbializing particle è" (gram p. 30), but this is limited to these 6 or so words, is not productive, and can be explained historically (due to either glottal dissimilation rule or analogy; see gram p. 30). examples include:

ši + è --> [ší è]

yellow P_{adv} 'yellowly'

nɔ + è --> [nɔ́ è]

blue P_{adv} 'bluey'

chu + è --> [chú è]

fat P_{adv} 'fatly'

-Particles are bound morphemes (because they cannot appear in a phrase on their own) with abstract grammatical functions, but are considered separate words as they are phonologically free (art p. 212); they always directly follow their 'hosts.'

Examples include:

yò (sentence adverbial declarative particle) as in: *Lâhū-yâ yò* 'He is a Lahu.'

thâʔ (object (typically indirect) noun particle) as in:

lîʔ chi ɲâ thâʔ pî tã ve yò

book this 1s OBJ give Pv Pu Puf

'(someone) has given me that book'

(without *thâʔ* this would mean 'I have given someone that book')

But, as shown above, the particles ò and è are not always phonologically free!

HOWEVER, with the above exceptions (the various particles with the form /è/, the verb particle /ò/ and the double vowel rule), there is no fusion across morpheme boundaries in Lahu.

Pausing rules (could this also be evidence for the domain for P- ω as an entire clause??):

Two kinds of pauses: comma pause, sentence pause

-comma pause:

-perhaps 1 mora long

-occurs optionally:

1. between NPs

2. between NP and VP

3. after non-final clause in complex sentences

4. "in certain special environments in sentences of complex structure" (gram. sec. 6.49)

-may NOT occur:

1. within an NP or VP

2. sentence-final

3. within a genitive construction (one main NP within which 2 NPs can coincide)

-sentence pause:

-somewhat longer than a comma pause

-optionally preceded by prolongation of the vowel of the preceding syllable if it is non-checked

-otherwise not associated with any particular intonational contour, pitch or stress.

-only in sentence-final position

Reduplication is common among nouns and has several forms as well as semantic effects. All autonomous nouns (except pronouns and the determiner) as well as several sorts of limited nouns such as classifiers and extentives are reduplicable.

!Here, reduplication is the ONLY phonological effect!

The different kinds of reduplication are as follows (art p. 210-211):

- 'Inclusive' reduplication indicates all member of the class represented by the noun

total reduplication: *yâ-mî yâ-mî* 'all the women'

- 'sequential' or 'distributive' shows how things represented by the noun are considered one

after the other

total: ɔ̂-cɛ ɔ̂-cɛ 'pair by pair'

-‘indefinite’ shows uncertainty about the scope

partial: tɛ̂ *chi kilô-lô* ‘about ten kilos’

-‘emphatic’ intensifies a noun

partial: ɔ̂-lɛ-lɛ ‘the very last’

-bisyllabic noun compounds can be reduplicated in the following pattern, in which case they become adverbial expressions (gramm p. 81, 314):

A-A=B-B

co-tāy ‘eternity’ --> *co-co-tāy-tāy* ‘eternally’

-in addition, there are hundreds of four-element reduplication compounds (‘elaborate expressions’) whose structure is as follows and which typically imply formality or elegance (art p. 210):

either A-B-A-C or A-B-C-B

examples:

qhɔ̂-qhô ‘in the mountains’ --> *qhɔ̂-qhô-lò-qhô* ‘in the mountains and valleys’

mû-mì ‘country’ --> *chi-mû-chi-mì* ‘this land of ours’

mêʔ-ní ‘red eyes’ --> *mêʔ-ní-mêʔ-qa* ‘red and smarting eyes’

This variety of reduplication (‘compound ionization’) often results in a violation of the ordinary rules of Lahu syntax because ‘a normally indissoluble bisyllabic compound is split up by inserting an identical element before or after each of its syllables’.

-This seems to imply that $\sigma = P-\omega$ since even breaking up a word doesn’t change the tones of the original individual syllables, or since the lexical word doesn’t have to have a specific tonal pattern.

-Most Lahu compounds have only 2 or 3 syllables (usually consisting of two root morphemes), but are occasionally (especially for flora and fauna names) 5 or 6 syllables long. And, as mentioned above, reduplication can occur in addition to this.

-So, with the couple exceptions as listed above, Lahu morphemes are basically composed of tone-bearing syllables which do not change any aspect of their phonological form when in combination.